

Fertility Patterns and Differential in India

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Abstract

Fertility rate plays an important role in the demographic context of India, showing considerable variation among women of reproductive age (15–49 years). The study aims to analyse fertility patterns and differentials in India and to identify the factors influencing them.

This paper uses data from five rounds of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS), covering 25 states of India. Missing data between survey rounds and for NFHS-1 were estimated using interpolation. To examine fertility patterns and differentials, age-specific fertility rate (ASFR) and total fertility rate (TFR) were used. In addition, a panel data regression analysis was conducted to determine the influence of various demographic and socioeconomic factors on fertility, using EViews 12 software.

Both ASFR and TFR follow a consistent pattern, with an initial peak followed by a decline over time. The panel data regression analysis revealed that residence, education, religion, birth order, unmet need for family planning, and sex preference are the most significant variables explaining variations in fertility levels.

Empirical evidence of fertility variations associated with specific factors raises concerns about population growth and women's reproductive health in India. The findings suggest that targeted policies and programs should be developed with a focus on these determinants in order to reduce fertility disparities and promote reproductive well-being.

Keywords

Demographic trends, Fertility, General welfare and well-being, Panel data models, Public policy, Rural

JEL codes: J11, J13, I31, C23, J18, O18

Introduction

In today's context, fertility rates play a crucial role in shaping population growth and women's reproductive health. The fertility rate refers to the total number of children a woman would bear by the end of her reproductive period, based on age-specific fertility rates for a given year (The World Bank ... 2024). These rates vary both between and within regions, communities, and countries due to a range of influencing factors.

This study examines 25 Indian states and utilizes statistical data from all five waves of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS), conducted between 1992–1993 and 2019–2021. For the first time, the influence of three key factors on fertility across these states has been estimated. Analysing differences across India is essential due to the substantial demographic, social, and economic diversity among states.

According to the Sample Registration System (SRS), fertility indicators such as the total fertility rate (TFR) have shown a marked decline: from 5.2 to 4.5 between 1971 and 1981, and from 3.6 to 2.0 between 1991 and 2020 (SRS 2013; SRS 2020). In rural areas, the TFR decreased from 5.4 to 2.2 between 1971 and 2019, while in urban areas it fell from 4.1 to 1.6. Between 1990–1992 and 2019–2021, the national TFR reached two children per woman – the replacement level of fertility (Our World in Data, 2024), according to NFHS data (IIPS 1995; IIPS 2022).

However, in states such as Bihar, Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh, and Manipur, the TFR remains above the replacement level (over 2.1), whereas in states such as Assam, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan, it has already fallen below this threshold. Additionally, projections from SRS and IIPS suggest that India's TFR, which declined from 3.1 in 2001 to 2.0 in 2020, is expected to decrease further to 1.7 by 2041.

This study focuses on five rounds of the NFHS, including the most recent NFHS-5 (2019–2021). Previous research has not conducted a cross-sectional analysis comparing different survey periods across states. In contrast, this study provides a comprehensive and precise assessment of the factors influencing fertility across 25 states.

The objective of this paper is to offer a detailed analysis of fertility differentials and to statistically estimate three key factors contributing to fertility differences across India, using data from all five rounds of the NFHS.

Contemporary Theories on Fertility Transition

Few general theories have been proposed to explain fertility transition.

In the last 25 years of the 20th century, industrialized countries experienced a new phase of fertility transition, in which birth rates or fertility rates fell below replacement levels, accompanied by a decline in death rates or mortality rates. This phase is known as the Second Demographic Transition Model (Lesthaeghe 1991; Van de Kaa 1987). The model is characterized by changes in variables such as marriage patterns, fertility, contraception, and lifestyle in European countries.

Changes in marriage patterns include the postponement of marriage, an increase in the age at first marriage, a rise in non-marital cohabitation, higher divorce rates, and a growing number of couples having only one child. In terms of fertility, the age at which women have their first child has increased, and the age group with the highest fertility has shifted upward. Greater access to contraception and birth control methods has enabled couples

to plan the number of children they have. Finally, changes in lifestyle have been linked to declines in mortality rates.

R. Easterlin developed a model explaining the association between fertility levels and relative cohort size. This relationship is influenced by fertility rates and changes in relative income (such as wages and unemployment). The theory suggests that fertility follows a cyclical pattern driven by both sociological and economic factors, where large birth cohorts tend to produce smaller subsequent cohorts. According to this hypothesis, a small cohort (within a 20-year period) tends to experience higher fertility, better job market prospects, and a higher standard of living. Conversely, a large cohort size, after 20 years, limits intended fertility, delays marriage and childbearing, and ultimately results in lower fertility (Doliger 2004).

Caldwell's theory of intergenerational wealth flows (Caldwell 1976) highlights the fertility transition from pre-industrial to industrial and post-industrial societies, with a focus on the economic role of children. In less-developed economies, particularly agricultural societies, children are considered economic assets, contributing labor to the family. In contrast, in highly developed countries, the rising costs of raising and educating children make them financial liabilities. This theory also emphasizes how social and cultural norms in traditional and agrarian societies often encourage larger families, whereas modern societies tend to favor smaller families.

As societies transition from pre-industrial to post-industrial stages, fertility rates tend to decline. This shift is particularly evident as education becomes more accessible, especially for women. Educated women often delay marriage and motherhood in favor of career development and personal growth. Fertility rates decrease as women gain greater economic and personal autonomy, along with increased access to family planning. According to this theory, both families and societies worldwide frequently view fertility as a sign of wealth and prosperity. Moreover, the theory provides a valuable framework for formulating policies that promote social justice, sustainable development, and gender equality (Kaplan & Bock 2001).

The quantity-quality trade-off was explained by Gary Becker in his "Becker model." According to this approach, children are viewed as commodities that provide utility through both their quantity and quality. The "quality" of children refers to the investments and resources parents allocate to them, such as education and upbringing. Wealthier parents can afford to invest more in their children, as expenditures typically increase with income. However, as income rises, the demand for additional children tends to decrease. In the United States, the 20th century witnessed a rise in child quality, driven by growing demand for educated workers. As a result, many parents chose to have fewer children, prioritizing higher quality of upbringing and education over the number of children (Doepke 2015).

The Theoretical Framework of Fertility

Before the onset of industrialization, women in India had, on average, five to six children over their lifetime. Fertility rates remained high into the early 19th century but began to change as fertility behavior varied across states and regions. By the second half of the 20th century, fertility started to decline rapidly. By 2019–2021, fertility rates had dropped to an average of two children per woman (IIPS 2022), well below the replacement level, marking a significant fertility transition during this period.

This decline in fertility rates is linked to several factors, including a rise in the age at first marriage, the prevalence of non-marital cohabitation, higher divorce rates, an increase in the number of couples having only one child, a shift in the age at first birth, and a change in the peak fertility age group from 20–24 years to 25–29 years. Additionally, widespread access to contraception and birth control, along with lifestyle changes, has played a major role in this fertility transition (Lesthaeghe 1991; Van de Kaa 2002).

In pre-industrial India, children were primarily regarded as economic assets, and social and cultural norms favored larger families. However, after industrialization, the cost of raising and educating children increased, turning them into financial liabilities for parents, who consequently preferred to have fewer children. Moreover, as education became more accessible for women, they gained greater autonomy in decisions regarding the postponement of marriage, utilization of family planning, and prioritization of their careers and personal development (Caldwell 1976; Kaplan & Bock 2001).

Data Sources & Methodology

The analysis of fertility patterns and differentials, along with an examination of factors such as caste, wealth index, and mortality rates influencing these patterns, was conducted using data from all five rounds of the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) in India: NFHS-1 (1992–1993), NFHS-2 (1998–1999), NFHS-3 (2005–2006), NFHS-4 (2015–2016), and NFHS-5 (2019–2021). Missing data from intervening years were estimated through interpolation.

The dependent variable in this analysis is the total fertility rate (TFR), representing the number of children a woman would have by the end of her reproductive period if she were to bear children according to current age-specific birth rates. The explanatory variables include residence, education, religion, contraceptive use, birth order, age at first marriage, birth interval, unmet need for family planning, and sex preference.

Unit Root Test

Before conducting the empirical analysis, a panel unit root test was performed to assess the stationarity of each series. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test evaluates the null hypothesis that a series is non-stationary against the alternative hypothesis that it is stationary, both at levels and first differences, with a constant term but without trend specification.

Estimation of Model

To examine the influence of various factors on fertility, a panel data regression model was employed using all five rounds of NFHS data for 25 states in India, analyzed with EVIEWS 12 software. Each factor, except for fertility rate, contraceptive use, age at first marriage, and birth interval, is categorized as follows:

- Residence: Rural and Urban.
- Education: No education, Primary level, High School & above.
- Religion: Hindu and Muslim.
- Birth Order: First birth, Second birth, Third birth, Fourth or higher.

- Unmet Need for Family Planning: Unmet need for spacing and Unmet need for limiting.
- Sex Preference: Prefer more sons than daughters, Prefer more daughters than sons, Want at least one son, Want at least one daughter.

Panel data analysis is a widely used statistical method for analyzing data collected over multiple periods for the same individuals or entities. Key models for panel data include Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Fixed-Effect (FE) models, Random Effect (RE) models, and Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) models (Wooldridge 2016). The three primary panel analyses are the independent Pooled OLS regression model, the Fixed-Effect model, and the Random Effect model (Basumatary & Devi 2022).

To determine the most appropriate model for the analysis, three tests – the Lagrange Multiplier test, Chow test, and Hausman test – were conducted using EVIEWS 12. First, the Pooled OLS regression was performed, followed by the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test, specifically the Breusch-Pagan LM test, to assess the suitability of the Pooled OLS versus the Random Effect model. Here, the null hypothesis states the absence of a random effect, while the alternative hypothesis suggests its presence. If the null hypothesis is rejected, a Fixed-Effect model is run, followed by the Chow test (Likelihood Ratio Test) to compare the Pooled OLS and Fixed-Effect models.

If the Chow test also rejects the null hypothesis, a Random Effect model is then estimated, followed by the Hausman test to compare the Random Effect and Fixed-Effect models. In this case, the null hypothesis posits the presence of a random effect, while the alternative hypothesis indicates the absence of a fixed effect. If the Hausman test accepts the null hypothesis, the Random Effect model is deemed suitable; otherwise, the Fixed-Effect model is chosen.

Additionally, tests for autocorrelation and multicollinearity were performed to provide statistical support for the panel data regression analysis.

The panel data regression model is specified as:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N$; $t = 1, \dots, T$; y_{it} – the dependent variable; X – the independent variable(s); β_i – the coefficients of the independent variables; α_i – the state-specific random effect (time-invariant); ε_{it} – the idiosyncratic error.

Results

The Fertility Pattern and Differential in India

The age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) for different regions in India are illustrated in Figure 1. It is evident that ASFRs are higher in rural areas compared to urban areas across various age groups, although they have been continuously declining in both settings over the years. The childbearing period for women, typically ranging from ages 15 to 49, reveals distinct fertility rates across different age groups.

The ASFR exhibits a notable pattern: it starts very low in the youngest age group (15–19), peaks in the 20–24 age group, and then gradually declines until reaching near zero in the 45–49 age group. Moreover, the ASFR for the rural population consistently shows a higher peak than that of the urban population. Slight variations in fertility patterns can be attrib-

Figure 1. Age-specific fertility rate in India from the 15–19 to 45–49 age groups. *Source:* National Family Health Survey-5, 2019–2021.

uted to factors such as age at first marriage, levels of contraceptive prevalence, desired family size, women’s societal status, and the extent of women’s participation in the workforce, among others.

Typically, the age pattern of fertility follows a bell-shaped curve; however, the exact shape of this curve varies between populations due to influences such as the age of women at marriage, levels of physiological sterility, marriage rates, incidences of widowhood and separation, customs regarding lactation and postpartum abstinence, and contraceptive use (Balasubramanian 1980).

The TFR (Total Fertility Rate) for all of India has shown a significant decline, decreasing from 3.39 children per woman in 1992–1993 to 2.85 in 1996–1998, 2.68 in 2005–2006, 2.18 in 2015–2016, and finally to 1.99 in 2019–2021, as illustrated in Figure 2. This decline is evident in both rural and urban areas. In 1992–1993, the fertility rate was 2.70 in urban areas and 3.67 in rural areas. By 1996–1998, these rates had decreased to 2.27 in urban areas and 3.07 in rural areas. By 2019–2021, the rates further declined to 1.63 in urban areas and 2.14 in rural areas, representing reductions of 39.6% in urban areas and 41.7% in rural areas.

On average, Indian women gave birth to two children (1.99) in 2019–2021, down from three children (2.85) in 1996–1998, indicating a decline of approximately 41.3%. This trend reflects a consistent pattern in the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) from NFHS-1 to NFHS-5. Initially, the TFR across India was slightly higher, followed by a steady decline. Similarly, both rural and urban areas experienced a peak in TFR that subsequently decreased. Notably, the TFR for the rural population remains higher compared to that of the urban population.

Figure 2. Pattern of the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) in India. *Source:* NFHS, 1992–1993 to 2019–2021.

Panel Unit Root Test

The data series at levels and first differences were tested for stationarity using Augmented Dickey – Fuller (ADF) tests. In this analysis, the data series for each state were evaluated both at levels and at first differences for stationarity through the individual unit root ADF Fisher test. According to the results presented in Table A1 (Appendix), the tests indicate that all individual series, except for total fertility rate, no education, primary education, high school or above education, any method of contraception, unmet need for spacing, preference for more sons than daughters, preference for more daughters than sons, and desire for at least one daughter, accept the null hypothesis at the level ($p > 0.05$), indicating that they are non-stationary. However, these series appear to be stationary at the first difference.

Panel Estimation

The results of the Breusch – Pagan LM test indicate that the null hypothesis is rejected at $p < 0.05$, suggesting that the pooled OLS model is not suitable for the analysis. Subsequently, the Chow test (Likelihood Ratio Test) was conducted, resulting in the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Furthermore, the Hausman test results show acceptance of the null hypothesis, implying that the random effects regression is the most appropriate model for factors such as residence, education, and religion. Conversely, the alternative hypothesis of fixed effects is accepted, indicating that the fixed effects regression is the better model for factors including contraceptive use, birth order, birth interval, unmet need for family planning, and sex preference when compared to the random effects regression. These results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The estimated random effect model is given by:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \beta_5 X_{5it} + \beta_6 X_{6it} + \beta_7 X_{7it} + (\alpha_i - \alpha) + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (1)$$

where Y_{it} – Total Fertility Rate, it – dependent variable; i – states, t – time periods; X_{1it} (Rural), X_{2it} (Urban), X_{3it} (No education), X_{4it} (Middle education), X_{5it} (High school & above), X_{6it} (Hindu), X_{7it} (Muslim) – independent variables; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7$ – the coefficients of the independent variables; ε_{it} – error term; α – the overall (common) intercept across all states and time periods; α_i – state-specific effect, capturing the unique characteristics of each state.

The estimated fixed effect model is:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \beta_5 X_{5it} + \beta_6 X_{6it} + \beta_7 X_{7it} + \beta_8 X_{8it} + \dots + \beta_{13} X_{13it} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (2)$$

where X_{1it} – any method of contraception; X_{2it} – first birth order; X_{3it} – second birth order; X_{4it} – third birth order; X_{5it} – fourth birth order; X_{6it} – median age at first marriage (25–49 years); X_{7it} – preceding birth interval (median months); X_{8it} – unmet need for spacing; X_{9it} – unmet need for limiting; X_{10it} – preference for more sons than daughters; X_{11it} – preference for more daughters than sons; X_{12it} – desire for at least one son; X_{13it} – desire for at least one daughter = the independent variables; $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{13}$ – coefficients of the independent variables; ε_{it} – error term; α_i – state-specific effect, capturing the unique characteristics of each state

The analysis of the estimated results reveals that the TFR is higher in rural areas (0.153751) compared to urban areas (-0.162595), indicating that rural women exhibit higher fertility rates than their urban counterparts.

Table 1. Results of estimated Random effect model

Dependent Variable: TFR

Method: Panel Least Squares

Cross-sections included: 25

Total panel (balanced) observations: 100

	Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Prob.
	C	-0.122062	0.197071	-0.619381	0.5372
Residence	Rural	0.153751	0.079744	1.928041	0.0569***
	Urban	-0.162595	0.109472	-1.485265	0.1409
Education	No education (illiterate)	0.401354	0.064909	6.183355	0.0000*
	Primary education	0.244216	0.077679	3.143922	0.0022*
	High school or above education	0.354777	0.103669	3.422202	0.0009*
Religion	Hindu	0.578533	0.076337	7.578641	0.0076*
	Muslim	0.125636	0.039131	3.210657	0.6965
	R ²		0.831339		
	Durbin – Watson stat.		1.474463		

Notes: * 1% level of significance, ** 5% level of significance, *** 10% level of significance. Source: authors' estimations based on NFHS, 1992–1993 to 2019–2021

Table 2. Results of estimated fixed effect model

Dependent Variable: TFR

Method: Panel Least Squares

Cross-sections included: 25

Total panel (balanced) observations: 100

	Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Prob.
	C	1.901719	0.810144	2.347385	0.0221
Contraceptive use	Any method of contraception	0.009345	0.006636	1.408371	0.1640
Birth order	First Birth Order	-0.032471	0.014016	-2.316619	0.0238**
	Second Birth Order	-0.007677	0.016971	-0.452344	0.6526
	Third Birth Order	-0.027726	0.017966	-1.543226	0.1279
	Fourth or more Birth Order	-0.009401	0.009557	-0.983629	0.3291
Age at first marriage	Median age at first marriage from age group 25 to 49	0.004761	0.020887	0.22796	0.8204
Birth interval	Since the preceding birth interval of the median number of months	-0.000804	0.014987	-0.053662	0.9574
Unmet need for family planning	Unmet need for spacing	0.068188	0.03049	2.236429	0.0289**
	Unmet need for limiting	0.024531	0.01552	1.580597	0.1191
Sex preference	preference for more sons than daughters	0.035821	0.007451	4.807252	0.0000*
	preference for more daughters than sons	-0.059287	0.030207	-1.962717	0.0542***
	desire for at least one son	-0.001302	0.006083	-0.214076	0.8312
	desire for at least one daughter	-0.011909	0.009324	-1.277255	0.2063
R ²			0.883332		
Durbin – Watson Stat.			2.328714		

Notes: * 1% level of significance, ** 5% level of significance, *** 10% level of significance. Source: authors' estimations based on NFHS, 1992–1993 to 2019–2021.

When examining the impact of education, it is observed that TFR is highest among illiterate women (0.401354), followed by women with a high school education or above (0.354777). These results suggest that fertility rates decline as women's education levels increase.

Additionally, the estimated results indicate that the TFR among Hindu women is higher than that of Muslim women; however, the slope coefficient for Muslim women is not statistically significant.

The use of any method of contraception is found to have a positive but statistically insignificant effect on fertility. Regarding birth order, the first birth has a negative and significant impact on the fertility rate, indicating that, on average, a 1% increase in first births is associated with a 0.03% decline in TFR. In contrast, the second, third, and fourth (or higher) birth orders show negative but statistically insignificant effects.

According to the estimation results, the median age at first marriage (25–49 years) shows a positive but insignificant association with TFR. Furthermore, the preceding birth interval – measured in median months – negatively affects fertility, although this effect is not statistically significant. Conversely, the unmet need for family planning and the unmet need for spacing have a positive and significant influence on TFR, increasing it by 0.068%.

On the other hand, the unmet need for limiting has a positive effect on the TFR, although this effect is statistically insignificant. Regarding sex preferences, the desire for more sons than daughters is found to have a positive and highly significant effect on the fertility rate, indicating that a one percent increase in this preference is associated with a 0.03% increase in the fertility rate. In contrast, the preference for more daughters than sons also has a positive influence on the fertility rate, but this effect is not statistically significant. Additionally, the desire for at least one son and the desire for at least one daughter both show negative effects on the fertility rate; however, these effects are also statistically insignificant.

Discussion

The present study analyzes the patterns and differentials of fertility, as well as the influence of key factors – residence, education, religion, contraceptive use, birth order, birth interval, unmet need for family planning, and sex preference – on fertility in the states of India using data from five rounds of the NFHS. According to the latest NFHS data, fertility in India is below the replacement level (2 children per woman) overall, as well as in both rural (2.1 children per woman) and urban (1.6 children per woman) areas. However, in some states such as Bihar, Meghalaya, Uttar Pradesh, and Manipur, fertility remains above the replacement level. Therefore, it is essential to examine the factors influencing fertility patterns and differentials among women of reproductive age.

Fertility among women of reproductive age is higher in rural areas than in urban areas, with the highest levels observed in the 20–24 age group. Fertility declines after the 30–34 age group and approaches nearly zero by ages 45–49. Additionally, the TFR has shown consistent rural–urban differences across India. In 1992–1993, the TFR was 2.7 in urban areas and 3.7 in rural areas, compared to 1.6 and 2.1, respectively, in 2019–2021. These differences are likely associated with variations in the age at first marriage, contraceptive prevalence, desired family size, women's socio-economic status, participation in non-household employment, and broader social and cultural norms related to childbearing.

Consistent with previous research, the present study also finds higher fertility in rural compared to urban areas. This result aligns with earlier studies conducted in West Bengal, India (Chouhan et al. 2020), Ethiopia (Dana 2018), and Nepal (Adhikari 2010). These disparities may be attributed to the higher financial cost and greater parental investment required to raise and educate children in urban settings compared to rural ones (Adhikari 2010). Women in urban areas generally have better access to services and resources, which promotes higher contraceptive use (Adhikari 2010; Retherford & Thapa 2003). Furthermore, rural women tend to marry at younger ages than their urban counterparts (Zarate 1967).

Women in the reproductive age group of 15 to 49 years with higher levels of education tend to have lower fertility rates compared to those with only primary or no education. Our findings are consistent with previous studies conducted in India, Nepal (Adhikari 2010), and Uganda (Ariho & Nzabona 2019). Educated women are more likely to delay marriage (Reddy 2003), extend the interval between marriage and childbirth (Roy & Hossain 2017), use contraception, and have smaller family sizes compared to uneducated women (Castro Martin 1995). Additionally, education significantly influences women's fertility behavior (Bbaale & Mpuga 2011), since women who attain secondary education or higher are more exposed to information, have greater autonomy in employment and marriage-related decisions, and are more aware of their own reproductive health and that of their children (Adhikari 2010).

According to previous studies (Balasubramanian 1984; Das & Pandey 1985; Arokiasamy 2002; Mari Bhat & Zaveri 1999; Adhikari 2010), Muslim women had higher fertility than Hindu women. However, our findings reveal that Hindu women exhibit higher fertility rates than Muslim women, although the coefficient for Muslim women is not statistically significant. This fertility rates differ among religious groups and it may be attributed to religious restrictions, cultural conservatism, and a lack of adequate knowledge or misconceptions about modern family planning methods, all of which can influence the acceptance or rejection of family planning (Albsoul-Younes et al. 2003). Moreover, low levels of education among Muslim women have been identified as a key factor contributing to higher fertility (Jeffery & Jeffery 2002). Additional factors such as early marriage, strong son preference, and the practice of polygamy may also contribute to higher fertility among Muslim women, as they can lead to competition among co-wives and consequently increase fertility levels (Sargent & Cordell 2003; Tafforeau et al. 1990).

Globally, contraceptive use has been a key determinant of fertility. However, our study found that the use of contraception has an insignificant effect on fertility. This may be because women who use contraception tend to have fewer children than those who do not, and contraceptive adoption often increases with rising levels of education. Additionally, women residing in urban areas are more likely to use contraceptives due to better access to health-related facilities (Retherford & Thapa 2003).

Another important finding of this study is that birth order is positively associated with fertility. Women with higher birth orders tend to have larger families than women at the first birth order, a result consistent with previous research in India. Children born at higher birth orders are also at greater risk of dying during infancy and early childhood (Determinants and Consequences... 2010; Howell et al. 2016).

The age at first marriage is positively associated with fertility, though the association is not statistically significant. A lower age at marriage tends to extend the childbearing period, and, in the context of lower contraceptive use, this often results in higher fertility rates. Several studies in India have observed a decline in fertility rates as the mean age at marriage increases (Borkotoky & Unisa 2015; IIPS 2007). Conversely, older age at marriage is associated with reduced fertility, as women who marry later are more likely to have attended school, be employed, use contraceptives, and maintain more equitable relationships with their husbands (Som & Mishra 2020; Bbaale & Mpuga 2011). In contrast, early marriage often leads to higher fertility, particularly in developing countries with limited contraceptive use. This situation can reduce access to education and increase the likelihood of high-risk or unwanted pregnancies, negatively affecting the health of both mother and child (Balakrishnan 1987).

Research findings suggest that birth interval has an insignificant direct effect on fertility. However, longer birth intervals are associated with improved child survival rates. A preced-

ing birth interval of less than 18 months doubles the risk of infant mortality compared to intervals of 36 months or longer (Fotso et al. 2013; Potter 1988). Women who already have a son tend to have longer birth intervals than those without a son (Khan et al. 2016). Conversely, the death of a preceding child shortens the interval before the next birth, as women often attempt to conceive again sooner (Khan et al. 2016; Kamal & Pervaiz 2012). Women from high-wealth families tend to have significantly longer birth intervals, influenced by factors such as education and lifestyle (Kamal & Pervaiz 2012). Less-educated women generally have shorter birth intervals compared to their educated counterparts, who are more likely to use contraception to extend birth spacing. This difference is largely due to greater awareness among educated women of the negative effects of short birth intervals and the benefits of smaller family sizes (Som & Mishra 2020; Tulasidhar 1993).

Our study also found that unmet need for family planning has a significant effect on fertility rates. An increase in unmet need for family planning is associated with higher fertility (Akram et al. 2020). The unmet need for spacing is particularly common among younger women, as observed in NFHS-2 (1998–1999) in Maharashtra. This trend may be attributed to a higher proportion of illiterate married women, who often lack access to information and may fear potential side effects. Additionally, barriers related to contraception – such as limited availability and low awareness – along with fertility-related factors such as lactational amenorrhea, desire for more children, and sex preference, also play a role. Opposition from husbands and other family members, religious beliefs, and low socio-economic status further contribute to the persistence of unmet need (Akram et al. 2020; Wulifan et al. 2017; Rahman 2016; Patil et al. 2005; Khokhar & Mehra 2005; Westoff 1978).

With regard to sex preferences, our study found that women who desire more sons than daughters exhibit higher fertility rates. Son preference is particularly pronounced among older women, who often have more children and may have experienced the death of a child (Barman & Sahoo 2021). Sons are frequently viewed as productive assets in family farms or businesses, as providers of security during emergencies and in their parents' old age, and as successors who carry on the family name and perform various ancestral rites. Additionally, analyses of state- and district-level data suggest that lower son preference in the southern states of India is an important factor contributing to reduced fertility rates in those regions (Drèze & Murthi 2001).

Conclusion

This study revealed significant patterns and differentials in fertility across age groups in India. Fertility differences were observed across multiple demographic categories and were influenced by several key factors. The main determinants shaping fertility patterns and differentials include place of residence (rural vs. urban), education level (no education, primary, high school or above), religion (Hindu), birth order (particularly first birth order), unmet need for family planning (especially unmet need for spacing), and sex preference (a desire for more sons than daughters or more daughters than sons).

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to strengthen efforts aimed at reducing fertility disparities among the states of India. Therefore, government agencies and relevant organizations should assess and implement policies that effectively address these differentials.

Abbreviations

NFHS: National Family Health Survey

TFR: Total Fertility Rate

ASFR: Age-Specific Fertility Rate

ADF: Augmented Dickey – Fuller

OLS: Ordinary Least Square

FE: Fixed Effect

RE: Random Effect

FGLS: Feasible Generalized Least Square

LM: Lagrange Multiplier

References

- Adhikari R (2010) Demographic, socio-economic, and cultural factors affecting fertility differentials in Nepal. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 10: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-10-19>
- Akram R, Sarker AR, Sheikh N, Ali N et al. (2020) Factors associated with unmet fertility desire and perceptions of ideal family size among women in Bangladesh: Insights from a nationwide Demographic and Health Survey. *PLoS ONE* 15(5): e0233634. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233634>
- Albsoul-Younes AM, Saleh F, El-Khateeb W (2003) Perception of efficacy and safety as determinants for use and discontinuation of birth control methods in Muslim Jordanian women. *The European Journal of Contraception and Reproductive Health Care* 8(3): 156–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/ejc.8.3.156.161>
- Ariho P, Nzabona A (2019) Determinants of change in fertility among women in rural areas of Uganda. *Journal of Pregnancy* 2019: 429171. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6429171>
- Arokiasamy P (2002) Gender preference, contraceptive use and fertility in India: Regional and development influences. *International Journal of Population Geography* 8(1) 49–67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijpg.236>
- Balakrishnan NV (1987) Socio-economic determinants of differential fertility in Kerala [Sri Venkateswara University].
- Balasubramanian K (1980) Differential fertility in India: Evidence from a survey in Karnataka State. PhD thesis, Australian National University. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/1885/116996>
- Balasubramanian K (1984) Hindu-Muslim differentials in fertility and population growth in India: role of proximate variables. *Artha Vijnana* 26: 189–216. <https://doi.org/10.21648/arthavij/1984/v26/i3/116369>
- Barman P, Sahoo H (2021) Sex preference in India: Trends, patterns and determinants. *Children and Youth Services Review* 122: 105876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105876>
- Basumatary K, Devi M (2022) Pooled ols and fixed effect estimation of wage structure and differential in handloom sector: Choosing the better method. *Journal of Social Economics Research* 9(2): 137–46. <https://doi.org/10.18488/35.v9i2.3152>
- Bbaale E, Mpuga P (2011) Female education, contraceptive use, and fertility: Evidence from Uganda. *Consilience: The Journal of Sustainable Development*: 6(1): 20–47. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26167815>
- Borkotoky K, Unisa S (2015) Female education and its association with changes in socio-demographic behaviour: Evidence from India. *Journal of Biosocial Science* 47(5): 687–706. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002193201400039X>

- Caldwell JC (1976) Toward a restatement of demographic transition theory. *Population and Development Review* 2(3/4): 321–66. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1971615>
- Castro Martin T (1995) Women's education and fertility: results from 26 Demographic and Health Surveys. *Studies in Family Planning* 26(4): 187–202. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2137845>
- Chouhan P, Saha J, Zaveri A (2020) Covariates of fertility behavior among ever-married women in West Bengal, India: Analysis of the National Family Health Survey-4. *Children and Youth Services Review* 113: 104956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.104956>
- Dana DD (2018) Binary logistic regression analysis of identifying demographic, socioeconomic, and cultural factors that affect fertility among women of child bearing age in Ethiopia. *Science Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics* 6(3): 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.sjams.20180603.11>
- Das N., Pandey D. (1985) Fertility differentials by religion in India: an analysis of 1971 Census fertility data // *Canadian Studies in Population*: 12(2): 119. <https://doi.org/10.25336/p6w88v>
- Determinants and consequences of high fertility: A synopsis of the evidence (2010) *Portfolio Review*. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/27497>
- Doepke M (2015) Gary Becker on the quantity and quality of children. *Journal of Demographic Economics* 81(1): 59–66. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26422362>
- Doliger C (2004) The Easterlin hypothesis. *Historical Social Research* 29(3): 205–12. <https://doi.org/10.12759/hsr.29.2004.3.205-212>
- Drèze J, Murthi M (2001) Fertility, education and development: Evidence from India. *Population and Development Review* 27(1): 33–63. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2695154>
- Fotso JC, Cleland J, Mberu B, Mutua M, Elungata P (2013) Birth spacing and child mortality: An analysis of prospective data from the Nairobi urban health and demographic surveillance system. *Journal of Biosocial Science* 45(6): 779–98. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932012000570>
- Howell EM, Holla N, Waidmann T (2016) Being the younger child in a large African family: A study of birth order as a risk factor for poor health using the demographic and health surveys for 18 countries. *BMC Nutrition* 2: 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40795-016-0100-8>
- Jeffery P, Jeffery R (2002) A population out of control? Myths about Muslim fertility in contemporary India. *World Development* 30(10): 1805–22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(02\)00066-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(02)00066-9)
- Kamal A, Pervaiz MK (2012) Determinants of higher order birth intervals in Pakistan. *Journal of Statistics* 19: 54–82. URL: <https://jstatgcu.pk/index.php/jstat/article/view/110>
- Kaplan HS, Bock J (2001) Fertility theory: Caldwell's theory of intergenerational wealth flows. In: NJ Smelser, PB Baltes (eds) *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. Pergamon, 5557–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b0-08-043076-7/02174-4>
- Khan JR, Bari W, Latif AHMM (2016) Trend of determinants of birth interval dynamics in Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health* 16: 934. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3577-9>
- Khokhar A, Mehra M (2005) Contraceptive use in women from a resettlement area in Delhi. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine* 30(1). URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/45261882_Contraceptive_Use_in_Women_From_a_Resettlement_Area_in_Delhi
- Lesthaeghe R (1991) The Second demographic transition in Western countries: An Interpretation. In: KO Mason, A-M Jensen (eds) *Gender and Family Change in Industrialized Countries*. Oxford Academic, 17–62. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198289708.003.0002>
- Mari Bhat PN, Zaveri F (1999) Findings of National Family Health Survey: Regional analysis. *Economic and Political Weekly* 34(42/43): 3008–17. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4408531>
- Patil SS, Khan AR, Narayan KA (2005) Unmet needs for contraception in married women in a tribal area of India. *Malaysian Journal of Public Health Medicine* 10: 44–51. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264851176_Unmet_needs_for_contraception_in_married_women_in_a_tribal_area_of_India

- Potter JE (1988) Birth spacing and child survival: A cautionary note regarding the evidence from the WFS. *Population Studies* 42(3): 443–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0032472031000143576>
- Rahman S (2016) A comparative study on unmet need for contraception among married women of reproductive age in urban slums of Guwahati and rural area of Rani Block, Kamrup, Assam. *Indian Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Research* 5(3): 442–50. URL: <https://www.ijbamr.com/assets/images/issues/pdf/June%202016%20442-450.pdf.pdf>
- Reddy PH (2003) Women's education and human fertility in India. *Social Change* 33(4): 52–64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004908570303300404>
- Retherford RD, Thapa S (2003) Fertility in Nepal 1981–2000: Levels, trends, and components of change / East-West Center Working Papers: 111. URL: <https://www.eastwestcenter.org/sites/default/files/private/POPwp111.pdf>
- Roy S, Hossain SMI (2017) Fertility differential of women in Bangladesh demographic and health survey 2014. *Fertility Research and Practice* 3: 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40738-017-0043-z>
- Sargent C, Cordell D (2003) Polygamy, disrupted reproduction, and the state: Malian migrants in Paris, France. *Social Science and Medicine* 56(9): 1961–72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(02\)00216-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(02)00216-2)
- Som K, Mishra RP (2020) Education, caste and occupational differentials in fertility in India. *European Journal of Geography* 11(1). URL: <https://www.eurogeojournal.eu/index.php/egj/article/view/119>
- Tafforeau J, Damiba A, Maternowska MC (1990) Changes in Chad: the results of a KAP survey. *Biology and Society: the Journal of the Eugenics Society* 7(4): 194–202. URL: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12316708/>
- Tulasidhar VB (1993) Maternal education, female labour force participation and child mortality: evidence from the Indian census. *Health Transition Review* 3(2): 177–90. URL: <https://scispace.com/pdf/maternal-education-female-labour-force-participation-and-2111mh34f.pdf>
- van de Kaa DJ (1987) Europe's Second demographic transition. *Population Bulletin* 42(1): 1–59. URL: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12268395/>
- van de Kaa DJ (2002) The idea of a Second demographic transition in industrialized countries. Paper Presented at the 6th Welfare Policy Seminar of the National Institute of Population and Social Security, Tokyo. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:39639830>
- Westoff CF (1978) The unmet need for birth control in five Asian countries. *International Family Planning Perspectives* 4(1): 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2947521>
- Wooldridge JM (2016) *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (6th Edition). Cengage Learning India Pvt. Ltd. URL: <https://jaimedv.com/eco/4c1-ecomet/jeffrey-m-wooldridge--econometrics--book.pdf>
- Wulifan JK, Jahn A, Hien H, Ilboudo PC et al. (2017) Determinants of unmet need for family planning in rural Burkina Faso: A multilevel logistic regression analysis. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth* 17: 426. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-017-1614-z>
- Zarate AO (1967) Some factors associated with urban-rural fertility differentials in Mexico. *Population Studies* 21(3): 283–93. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2173147>

Other sources of information

- IIPS (1995) National Family Health Survey (NFHS-1) 1992–93. International Institute for Population Sciences, Bombay. URL: <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/SR162/SR162.pdf>
- IIPS (2007) National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3) 2005–06. India Report. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2296.6246>

- IIPS (2022) National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) 2019-21. Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India. URL: https://mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/NFHS-5_Phase-II_0.pdf
- Our World in Data (2024) Fertility rate, total UN WPP. UN, World Population Prospects (2024). <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/replacement-level-fertility>
- SRS (2013) Compendium of India's fertility and mortality indicators 1971-2013. Registrar General, India. URL: https://www.fertilitydata.org/File/GetFile/Raw/IND_01.pdf
- SRS (2020) Sample Registration System Statistical Report 2020. In Office of The Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India, Ministry of Home Affairs Government of India. URL: https://www.fertilitydata.org/File/GetFile/Raw/IND_21.pdf
- The World Bank Group (2024) Data Bank. URL: <https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/millennium-development-goals/series/SP.DYN.TFRT.IN>

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Appendix

Table A1. Panel Unit Root Test

Method: ADF Fisher Unit Root Test

Variables		Stationary at level		Stationary at the single difference	
		Statistic	Prob.	Statistic	Prob.
	TFR (Total Fertility Rate)	89.9	0.0004	NA	NA
Residence	Rural	59.7	0.1628	104.5	0.0000
	Urban	65.4	0.0706	94.4	0.0001
Education	No education (illiterate)	99.6	0.0000	NA	NA
	Primary level	148.2	0.0000	NA	NA
	High school or above level	141.5	0.0000	NA	NA
Religion	Hindu	31.6	0.9798	83.3	0.0021
	Muslim	27.1	0.9783	63.6	0.0101
Contraceptive use	Any method of contraception	67.4	0.05	NA	NA
Birth order	First Birth Order	28.9	0.9926	108.3	0.0000
	Second Birth Order	32.7	0.972	94.2	0.0002
	Third Birth Order	52.6	0.3737	155.8	0.0000
	Fourth or more Birth Order	41.6	0.7921	86.1	0.0011
Age at first marriage	Median age at first marriage (25-49 years)	42.2	0.7734	68.7	0.0405
Birth interval	The median number of birth interval	31.4	0.9815	73.2	0.0176
Unmet need for family planning	Unmet need for spacing	96.5	0.0001	NA	NA
	Unmet need for limiting	63.04	0.1018	77.1	0.0082
Sex preference	Want more sons than daughters	82.1	0.0028	NA	NA
	Want more daughters than sons	69.1	0.0378	NA	NA
	Want at least one son	65.1	0.0738	79.8	0.0046
	Want at least one daughter	70.03	0.0322	NA	NA

Source: authors' estimations based on NFHS, 1992–1993 to 2019–2021.